

Separation of Metal Ions by Thin Layer Chromatography with Salicylhydroxamic Acid as a Complexing Agent

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Salicylhydroxamic acid has been found suitable for the detection and separation of metal ions by thin layer chromatography. The metal ions which have been studied in this connection are U(VI), V(V), Mo(VI), Ti(IV), Fe(III), Mn(II), Cu(II), and Co(II). No developer to process the chromatograms are necessary as the metal hydroxamate complexes possess individual distinctive colours. The technique has been successfully applied for detection and subsequent rapid estimation of the elements in different ores and minerals.

THE thin layer chromatography, although a well established technique in the field of analysis and identification of organic compounds has been less frequently used in inorganic analysis²⁻⁷ in comparison to other chromatographic methods. Taking advantage of the better separability of organic substances in the thin layer media, organo-metallic compounds instead of simple metal ions have been tried as the migrating species. This communication describes a detailed thin layer chromatographic investigation of metal-salicylhydroxamic acid complexes and their movements in different solvents. It has resulted in developing a very suitable method for the separation and identification of mixtures of metal ions, specially of the transitional group, in a simple and convenient way. In addition to this the colours of the metal-hydroxamic acid complexes are utilised to distinguish and identify the various metal species rendering the use of developer spray to process the chromatogram unnecessary. This appreciably shortens the total time required for the measurement and helps in producing sharp and intensely coloured bands, undisturbed from the effects of spraying. A similar procedure has been successfully employed by the authors in circular paper chromatography with identical purpose¹.

Experimental

The stock solutions of the metals Fe(III), Ti(IV), V(V), U(VI), Mn(II), Mo(VI), Cu(II) and Co(II) were prepared from their corresponding analytical grade reagents.

Mixtures of solvents containing iso-butanol, iso-propanol, ethyl methyl ketone, ethyl alcohol, methyl alcohol, hydrochloric acid and ammonia were used. The reagent salicylhydroxamic acid (purified by repeated crystallisation) was used.

Glass plates coated with silica gel-G and alumina were utilised for the investigations.

No developer was used to process the chromatogram excepting ammonia gas or acid fumes.

Results

Solvent mixtures

- A. Salicylhydroxamic acid (0.153 gm) : Iso-propanol (99 ml) : 1M hydrochloric acid (1 ml)
- B. Salicylhydroxamic acid (0.153 g) : Iso-propanol (25 ml) : *n*-butanol (25 ml) : Ethyl alcohol (20 ml) : Ethyl methyl ketone (20 ml) : 1M Hydrochloric acid (10 ml)

Adsorbent used, Silica gel—G, 0.5 mm thick.

Separation of mixtures of metal ions

Solvent mixtures

- S₁. Salicylhydroxamic acid (0.153 g) : Isobutanol (90 ml) : 1M hydrochloric acid (10 ml). Time—1.5 hr.
- S₂. Salicylhydroxamic acid (0.153 g) : Isopropanol (99 ml) : 1M hydrochloric acid (1 ml). Time—2 hr.

Adsorbent used, Silica gel—G, 0.5 mm thick.

Discussion

The rates of migrations of Cu(II), Co(II), Fe(III), V(V), Mo(VI), and U(VI) complexes after complex formation with salicylhydroxamic acid, present in the solvent mixture, are quite distinct from each other which is evident from the R_f -values shown in Table I.

Some difficulties are encountered when mixture of metal solutions used for chromatographic separation on the thin layer plate, although forming distinctly coloured metal complexes fail to separate into well defined bands on the plate unlike those obtained on the paper. Some of the coloured bands overlap or leave some coloured trails. In spite of these the

TABLE 1

Metal ions	Colour	<i>R_f</i> -values with solvent mixture A, Time 2 hr.	<i>R_f</i> -values with solvent mixture B, Time 1.5 hr.	Developing Agent
Cu(II)	Green	0.22(Trail)	0.75	Original with NH ₃ -vapour
Co(II)	Dark-Brown	0.40	0.80	"
Mo(VI)	Yellow	0.47	0.70	"
U(VI)	Orange	0.21	0.71	"
V(V)	Violet	0.72	0.85	Original
Ti(IV)	Orange-yellow	No migration	0.30	"
Fe(III)	Pinkish	Diffused	Diffused	"

TABLE 2

Mixture of metal ions	Corresponding <i>R_f</i> -values	Developing agent	Remarks
1. S ₁ Co(II)-Mo(VI)-U(VI)	Co(0.70), Mo(0.67), U(0.65)	Original with NH ₃ -vapour	Clear separation
2. S ₁ Co(II)-Cu(II)-Fe(III)	Co(0.71), Cu(0.65), Fe(0.70)	"	"
3. S ₁ Fe(III)-U(VI)-Mo(VI)	Fe(0.95), U(0.95), Mo(0.94)	"	Close colour bands.
4. S ₁ V(V)-U(VI)-Mo(VI)-Ti(IV)	V(0.70), Ti(0.27)	Original	U, Mo colour bands overlapped.
5. S ₂ Fe(III)-Ti(IV)-V(V)	Fe(0.28), V(0.44)	"	Ti does not migrate
6. S ₂ Co(II)-Fe(III)-Ti(IV)-V(V)	Co(0.12), Fe(0.28), V(0.43)	"	"

widely divergent yet strong colours of the different metals make it possible to identify the metallic ions after separation on the plate (Table 2). When the colours of the metal complexes happen to be of similar nature it becomes rather difficult to identify the metal ions.

Thin layer plates prepared from alumina with starch binder when used for the study of metal ions like Cu(II), Co(II), Fe(III), Ti(IV), U(VI), V(V), Mo(VI) in different solvent mixtures were found to retard the migration of the coloured complex species formed on the plate.

The rates of migrations of these metal salicyl-hydroxamic acid complexes varies with the concentrations of acids, and the thickness of the plates. Some difficulties arise when the concentration of acid is increased in the solvent mixture when complexes of metals like titanium(IV), iron(III) and vanadium(V), show increased colour intensities whereas those of metals like uranium(VI), cobalt(II), copper(II) and molybdenum(VI) are faded out due to the breaking down of the corresponding complexes. An acid concentration 0.1M to 1.00M in the solvent mixture is found quite suitable for the movement of metal salicylhydroxamates.

This technique has been successfully applied to separate and detect the metal ions like titanium(IV),

copper(II) and iron(III) directly from the solutions of different ores and minerals by their distinctive colours.

Quantitative estimation of titanium

It has also been possible to estimate titanium quantitatively by scraping out the separated metal complex band on the thin layer plate, dissolving it in acid and measuring the colour with salicylhydroxamic acid^{8,9} at 348 nm.

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